

Metal elements analysis of fruits using inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometry coupled with microwave digestion

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Abstract : The objective of this work was to develop a method to determine the metal content in fruit samples from Xinxiang in China. Seven samples of fruit available in the supermarket were analyzed for the metals Mg, Ca, Fe, Cu, Zn, Al, B, Ni by inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometry (ICP-AES) coupled with microwave digestion. The Mg, Ca, Fe, Cu, Zn, Al, B, Ni concentrations were between 1182–3754, 1023–4100, 58.6–146, 15.6–32.7, 17.9–92.9, 26.7–100, 34.9–190 and 6.9–53.4 mg/kg, respectively. The method was precise (with RSD < 4.24%) and sensitive (LOD ranged between 0.0075 and 0.0652 µg/mL).

Keywords : Metal elements, fruit samples, microwave digestion, ICP-AES.

Introduction

Trace metals and nutrients are scientifically recognized as essential or potentially essential constituents for human health¹. Fruits are an important component of the human in traditional diet. They contain a lot of biologically active substances that have beneficial effects on human health as antioxidants, anticancerogens, antimutagens and antibacterial compounds^{2–5}. Fruits and leafy vegetables are believed to occupy a modest place as a source of trace elements due to their high water content. Most of nutrient requirements can be met by increasing the consumption of fruits and vegetables to 5–13 servings/day⁶. Fruits and vegetables have low energy content, while the nutrient densities are very high. Increased consumption of fruits and vegetables can help replace foods high in saturated fats, sugar and salt and thus improve the intake of most micronutrients and dietary fiber⁷. Daily consumption of fresh fruits and vegetables (4400 g/d) is recommended to help prevent major non-communicable diseases such as cardiovascular diseases and certain cancers⁸. Therefore, trace elements analysis of fruits is very important for the assessment of nutrition and environmental effects on humans. The environmental term includes origin of fruits,

such as the soil on which fruits or its ingredients are grown and reservation measures. In trace elements analysis of biological materials and food stuffs the digestion is the very basic step, which may include reduction in time and cost of methods of analysis, production of waste products and also possible reduction in energy consumption. The use of microwave radiation and high pressure allows to accelerate sample digestion and to minimize contamination and losses of volatile elements^{9–12}. Inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometry (ICP-AES) has become one of the most attractive detection systems for the determination of metal elements in plant materials and other biological samples^{13–16}.

The present work aimed was to determinate the metal element (Mg, Ca, Fe, Cu, Zn, Al, Ni, B) contents of some fruits commercially available in Xinxiang, China by ICP-AES coupled with microwave digestion method.

Results and discussion

Optimization of sample processing and digestion conditions :

The fruit samples contain a lot of water, the samples determined were pretreated using dry ashing method in

order to achieve real experimental results. Appropriate calcination temperature and calcination time of sample were optimized by a series of calcination experiments. The results showed the fruit samples were calcinated in a muffle furnace at 350 °C for 4 h. Then, a MAS microwave digestion system was used to digest the fruit samples powders calcinated. The magnetron mounted in the microwave oven can operate at a frequency of 2450 MHz. The operational parameters of the microwave digestion were showed in Table 1.

Blank values :

Blank values for the trace elements under study were also determined for the assessment of possible contamination level in the digestion procedure adopted. A set of three digestion vessels each containing 12.0 mL concentrated HNO₃ was subjected through the digestion procedure. After digestion and making up the volume to 25 mL with 3% HNO₃. The results showed these blank values of the trace elements were low and did not cause any problem during the determination of elements.

Optimization of spectrometric measurement :

The determination of various metal elements was performed by means of ICP-AES, which is known as a reliable measurement technique owing to multielement capability, wide linear working range and sufficiently low LODs for the majority of metal elements. Calibration

procedure was employed using 3% HNO₃ multielement standard solutions. Selecting the spectral lines for detecting, which must have little spectral interference and high precision. The following wavelength lines were used : Mg 279.07, Ca 317.93, Fe 259.93, Cu 324.75, Zn 213.85, Al 396.15, Ni 231.60 and B 249.77 nm.

Method validation :

Linearity was evaluated using the linear correlation coefficient (*r*) of a calibration curve (Calibration curve was performed using a series of multi-element calibration standard solutions). The LOD and LOQ were calculated by the standard 3 SD and 10 SD approaches and repeat analysis of blank solutions. The calibration plot showed good linearity and was represented by the calculated regression equation and correlation coefficients (*r*). The calculated regression equation and correlation coefficients (*r*), LOD and LOQ by ICP-AES method were showed in Table 2. The accuracy of the method was verified by analysing the certified reference material GBW 07604-Poplar leaves (China National Research Center for Certified Reference Materials). 0.3000 g GBW 07604-Poplar leaves was used. GBW 07604-Poplar leaves material was prepared and analyzed in the way described above. The result was showed in Table 3. As it can be seen, the results were found to be in good agreement with the certified values.

Table 1. The operational parameters of the microwave digestion

Stage	Power (W)	Temperature rise time (min)	Running temperature (°C)	Holding time (min)
1	800	5	100	3
2	800	3	120	5
3	800	6	130	15

Table 2. Calibrations and detection limits of the metal elements by ICP-AES

Element	Regression equation	Correlation coefficient (<i>r</i>)	LOD (µg/mL)	LOQ (µg/mL)
Mg	$Y = 3640X + 172.1$	0.99967	0.0433	0.1431
Ca	$Y = 31032X + 6025.4$	0.99933	0.0476	0.1575
Fe	$Y = 39125X + 62.1$	0.99989	0.0089	0.0295
Cu	$Y = 47622X + 1682.6$	0.99958	0.0075	0.0312
Zn	$Y = 28713X + 233.9$	0.99942	0.0080	0.0272
Al	$Y = 325404X + 4562.5$	0.99996	0.0652	0.2251
B	$Y = 92694X + 1138.7$	0.99997	0.0113	0.0393
Ni	$Y = 27253X + 160.2$	0.99993	0.0524	0.1731

Table 3. Results of the analysis with microwave digestion procedures of GBW 07604 – Poplar leaves certified reference material ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) ($n = 5$)

Element	Certified value	Determined value	RSD (%)
Mg	78	75 \pm 3.12	3.12
Ca	217.2	216.3 \pm 4.24	4.24
Fe	3.29	3.28 \pm 2.36	2.36
Cu	0.11	0.11 \pm 1.02	1.02
Zn	0.45	0.46 \pm 1.28	1.28
Al	12.48	12.45 \pm 2.43	2.43
B	0.64	0.44 \pm 2.47	2.47
Ni	0.02	0.02 \pm 2.31	2.31

Determination of metal content :

The metal element contents (Mg, Ca, Fe, Cu, Zn, Al, B, Ni) in the samples determined by ICP-AES was shown in Table 4. Metal element contents of samples were different in different fruit samples. The highest mean levels of Mg and Ca were found when compared with results of other elements in all samples determined. Mg contents varied from 1182 mg/kg apple to 5478 mg/kg pitaya. Ca contents ranged between 1023 mg/kg banana and 4100 mg/kg kiwi fruit. Magnesium plays an important role in improving metabolism in the human body, may have led to its usefulness in evolution as an ion for signaling, enzyme activation and catalysis. Inadequate magnesium intake frequently causes muscle spasms, and has been associated with cardiovascular disease, diabetes, high blood pressure, anxiety disorders, migraines, osteoporosis and cerebral infarction¹⁷. Important physiological roles for calcium signaling range widely. These include muscle contraction, neuronal transmission as in an excitatory synapse, cellular motility (including the movement of flagella and cilia), fertilisation, cell growth or proliferation, learning and memory as with synaptic

plasticity and secretion of saliva¹⁸. Fe is an essential mineral and an important component of proteins involves in oxygen transport and metabolism^{6,19}. Fe contents were found between 58.6 mg/kg banana and 575 mg/kg pitaya. The Fe concentration in previous studies was in the range of 3.89–40.7 mg/kg wet weight in various summer fruits of Pakistan²⁰, 6.76–64.1 mg/kg dry weight in dried fruits commonly consumed in Kayseri, Turkey²¹. Cu is known to be vital for many biological systems. In humans, copper is essential to the proper functioning of organs and metabolic processes. The human body has complex homeostatic mechanisms which attempt to ensure a constant supply of available copper, while eliminating excess copper whenever this occurs²². Cu forms part of at least 13 different enzymes, and its presence is needed for each if they are to function properly. In the present study, the mean levels of Cu ranged from 14.6 banana to 32.7 mg/kg mango. In the literature, copper levels in fruits from the Egyptian markets have been reported in the range 1.22–18.3 mg/kg²³. Zinc, which is present with certain concentrations in several fruits, is used in the treatment of shortness and other diseases and used in fruit juice industries²⁴. Zn amounts varied between 17.9 mg/kg apple and 92.9 mg/kg pitaya. Boron is the maintenance of bone health and calcium, phosphorus, magnesium and trace elements needed for normal metabolism. The highest and lowest values for B 190 mg/kg apple and 34.9 mg/kg banana. Nickel can stimulate the growth of blood, can promote the regeneration of red cells. All Ni contents of samples were found similar. The Ni value of pitaya was maximum (53.4 mg/kg) and the Ni value of banana (6.9 mg/kg) was minimum. Ni contents in the literature have been reported in the range of 1.0–8.9 mg/kg in summer fruits from Pakistan¹⁸. In addition, similar findings were

Table 4. Metal element contents of eight fruits (mg/kg; dried ash mass of the edible part)

Element	Pineapple	Apple	Grape	Pitaya	Mango	Kiwi fruit	Banana
Mg	3754	1182	1590	5478	2055	1993	2944
Ca	2899	1452	1605	1272	2844	4100	1023
Fe	112	113	136	146	59.1	61.6	58.6
Cu	15.6	19.7	31.5	23.9	32.7	22.5	14.6
Zn	32.2	17.9	24.2	92.9	37.6	26.5	33.4
Al	97.6	94.1	92.3	80.5	36.5	100	26.7
B	50.0	190	61.1	46.1	48.2	98.3	34.9
Ni	12.0	8.9	8.6	53.4	7.4	16.5	6.9

also reported for other fruit species. The contents of Cd, Pb, Cu, Mg and Zn in different species of domestic fruits have been determined by Ellen *et al.*²⁵. Hamurcu *et al.* researched the amounts of mineral and heavy metal levels of some fruits grown at the roadsides, Zn and Cu were found at the high levels in the fruit samples²¹. Altundag investigated levels of the multi element in some dried fruit samples by ICP-OES⁷. Some of our results for metal contents of the fruits showed minor differences when compared with the literature, the different probably due to the variety/cultivar, growth conditions, environmental, constructive factors, and analytical procedures.

Experimental

Samples :

The fruit samples of pineapple, apple, grape, pitaya, mango, kiwi fruit, banana were bought from the fruit product market in Xinxiang, China and authenticated by Doc. Benguo Liu (School of Food Science, Henan Institute of Science and Technology, Xinxiang, China). To minimize contamination, all the materials used in the experiments were previously washed with ultra-pure water (SG Ultra Clear system, Wasseraufbereitung und Regenerierstation GmbH, Germany).

Sample preparation and analysis :

After washing with ultra-pure water, the fruit samples were calcinated in a muffle furnace (SXL Program Control Muffle, Shanghai Jing Hong Laboratory Instrument Co., Ltd.) at 350 °C for 4 h. All samples calcinated were smashed using mortar, respectively. Three replicate powder samples (0.3000 g) of the same fruit were accurately weighed into the different digestion vessels, then, 12.0 mL concentrated HNO₃ (superior grade of pure, Zhengzhou Piney Chemical Reagent Factory) was added, samples were digested using MAS microwave digestion system (CEM Corporation of USA) according to the microwave digestion procedures optimized in Table 1. After the end of the microwave digestion procedures, the digestion solution was transferred into the corresponding beaker in order to reduce the acid concentration of digestion solution, and all the beakers were heated by a electric heating plate at 140 °C for 2 h. At last, the digestion solution was transferred into 25 mL volumetric flask and

made up the volume with 3% HNO₃. Concentrations of metal elements were determined by Optima2100 DV inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometry (ICP-AES, Perkin-Elmer Corporation, Norwalk, CT, USA). The operating conditions are summarized in Table 5.

Table 5. ICP-AES operating conditions

RF (MHz)	40.68
RF power (W)	1300
Gas flow rate (/min) :	
Plasma gas	15.0
Auxiliary gas	0.2
Nebulizer gas	0.58
Sample uptake rate (ml/min)	1.5
Observation height (mm)	15
Plasma viewing	Radial
Read time (s)	15
Delay time (s)	30
Wash time (s)	30

Preparation of mixed standard solutions :

Mixed standard solutions of 0.00, 0.5, 1.00, 2.00, 4.00 and 8.00 µg/mL (Mg, Ca, Fe, Cu, Zn, Al, B, Ni) were prepared by ICP-AES 23 multi-element standard stock solution diluted with 3% nitric acid.

Metal elements analysis :

Mg, Ca, Fe, Cu, Zn, Al, Ni and B were determined by ICP-AES. In the ICP-AES analysis, the method was validated for the determination of metal in fruits against the following performance criteria : linearity, the limit of detection (LOD), the limit of quantitation (LOQ) and accuracy.

Conclusion :

The microwave digestion is a simple, fast and reliable way to obtain complete digestion of fruit samples for the determination of Mg, Ca, Fe, Cu, Zn, Al, B and Ni. ICP-AES determination of metal elements in fruits enables a rapid analysis with good precision and accuracy. Results had differences with literature values. These differences are probably due to variety/cultivar, growth conditions, environmental, constructive factors, and analytical procedures.

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